

Studies on some Mixed-ligand Hydridocarbonyl Phosphine Complexes of Iridium(I)

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Manuscript received 22 January 1992, revised 16 December 1992, accepted 19 February 1993

The present study describes some mixed ligand hydridocarbonylphosphine complexes of iridium(I) with 1-substituted-tetrazoline-5-thione in view of their catalytic interest¹.

Results and Discussion

1-Phenyl (1PT5TH), 1-*o*-tolyl (1otT5TH) and 1-*m*-tolyl (1mtT5TH) derivatives of tetrazoline-5-thione from stable solid complexes with iridium(I) having general formula $[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{LH})_2]$ (LH = 1PT5TH, 1otT5TH or 1mtT5TH) and $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{LH})_2(\text{SnCl}_3)]$ (LH = 1mtT5TH). All the complexes (Table 1) are diamagnetic and decolourise violet solution of iodine in CCl_4 indicating d^8 -configuration (Ir^+). Their electronic spectra display a single very strong broad band at $42\,553\text{--}34\,014\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to charge transfer band². The other ligand field bands are obscured due to high intensity of CT band. However, two strong bands at $44\,248$ and $38\,168\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(1\text{mtT5TH})_2(\text{SnCl}_3)]$ are observed. The first band may be of charge transfer origin² and the second band presumably because of $^1a_{1g} \rightarrow ^1b_{1g}$ transition considering M.O. diagram³ of square-pyramidal C_{4v} group symmetry.

A comparison of the ir spectra of the complexes with those of the corresponding ligand indicates that strong metal-sulphur bonding results in a decrease in the frequency of thioamide band-IV⁴ by $40\text{--}60\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Moreover, the systematic change in position and intensity of other thioamide bands⁵ also supports iridium-sulphur bond. It appears that iridium-carbon bond is stronger in $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(1\text{mtT5TH})_2(\text{SnCl}_3)]$ and the carbonyl group is of shorter distance at apical position in square-pyramidal structure. The fact is substantiated by the positions of $\nu\text{C} \equiv \text{O}$ and $\nu\text{Ir-C}$ bands observed at higher frequencies in comparison to other complexes. However, the basal position of bulky ligands $\text{P}\phi_3$, SnCl_3 or 1-substituted-tetrazoline-5-thione seems to be reasonable considering steric preferences. The *trans*-arrangement for bulky heterocyclic ligand like 1-substituted-tetrazoline-5-thione may also be assumed considering a straight-jacket-effect.

Two weak bands at 465 and 440 cm^{-1} in the far-ir spectrum of $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(1\text{mtT5TH})_2(\text{SnCl}_3)]$ are assigned to $\nu\text{Sn-Cl}$ of coordinated SnCl_3 group⁶.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	M p °C	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)			
		C	H	N	Ir
$[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(1\text{PT5TH})_2]$ (Light straw)	72d	46.46 (46.31)	3.73 (3.74)	13.01 (13.09)	22.47 (22.45)
$[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(1\text{otT5TH})_2]$ (White)	250	47.32 (47.45)	3.60 (3.61)	13.01 (12.65)	21.67 (21.69)
$[\text{IrH}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(1\text{mtT5TH})_2]$ (French grey)	78d	47.22 (47.45)	3.63 (3.61)	12.33 (12.65)	21.34 (21.69)
$[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(1\text{mtT5TH})_2(\text{SnCl}_3)]$ (Beige)		38.35 (38.28)	2.81 (2.82)	10.19 (10.20)	17.68 (17.50)

Experimental

All chemical used were of C.P. grade. The ligand 1-substituted-tetrazoline-5-thione was prepared by the method reported in literature⁷. The complexes were prepared by stirring a suspension of IrCl_3 (0.05 mol), $\text{P}\phi_3$ (0.6 mol) and KCl (0.05 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) at 65° for 2 h. The mixture was then allowed to evaporate on a water-bath and the residue was suspended in a mixture of 1-substituted-tetrazoline-5-thione (0.1 mol) in benzene and monoethyl ether of ethylene glycol (1:1). The mixture was again stirred and kept at room temperature overnight. The resulting solid complexes were washed with methanol and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis were done at U.S.I.C., Delhi. Analyses of metal and chlorine were carried out using standard methods. Magnetic measurements were made by means of Gouy method at room temperature. The conductivity of the complexes ($10^{-3}M$ in DMF) was measured

with the help of a Sistrionic conductometer. Infrared and electronic spectra were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

References

1. L. VASKA and R. E. RHODES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 4970.
2. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1984, p. 354
3. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Field", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1966, p. 246.
4. C. N. R. RAO, R. VENKATARAGHAVAN and F. R. KASTURI, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 36.
5. B. SINGH, R. SINGH, R. V. CHOUDHARY and K. P. THAKUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 174.
6. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th ed., Wiley, New York, 1986, p. 325.
7. E. LIEBER and J. RAMCHANDRAN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1959, **37**, 101.
8. P. C. RAY and N. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 251.
9. F. P. TREADWELL and W. T. HALL, "Analytical Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1935, Vol. II, p. 307.